

Nutrition in Irish Healthcare Education: Gaps and Opportunities

Nutrition plays a central role in the prevention and management of many chronic conditions, influencing key risk factors such as obesity, hypertension and type 2 diabetes, yet relatively little attention has been paid to how it is represented within healthcare education. As these conditions continue to place pressure on health systems in Ireland and internationally, there is growing recognition of the need to strengthen nutrition capacity across the healthcare workforce. Primary care professionals are frequent points of contact within the health service and are widely regarded as trusted sources of health information. Ensuring they are equipped to provide consistent, evidence-based nutrition support is therefore an important consideration for patient care and population health.

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Research Overview

Published in the Public Health Nutrition journal in January 2026, this research explores how nutrition is represented within healthcare education in Ireland, focusing on curriculum frameworks, accreditation standards and professional registration requirements across disciplines such as medicine, nursing and allied health.

Using a document analysis approach, the study examines how nutrition is described and prioritised within formal educational structures. This research offers insight into the extent to which current standards supporting healthcare training explicitly recognise nutrition as a component of professional competence.

Key Insights / Findings

The findings highlight a limited and inconsistent presence of nutrition across healthcare education and professional standards in Ireland. Of the 52 education programmes reviewed, only 26.9% made direct reference to nutrition, with most of these occurring at postgraduate level rather than within core undergraduate training. In addition, only 20% of professional registration requirements explicitly referenced nutrition, while 50% of accreditation standards included direct references. Given the importance of nutrition in reducing disease risk factors, this suggests that many healthcare graduates may enter practice without formal, structured engagement with nutrition as a defined competency. This is particularly significant given the growing rates of diet-related chronic disease and the increasing emphasis on prevention within healthcare systems. At the same time, the research reflects documented standards only, and further analysis is needed to understand how these translate into teaching, learning and practice.

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Further Reading:

McMonagle G, Ryan L,
Doherty R, Keaver L. (2026)
Nutrition education for
healthcare professionals
in Ireland: insights from
curriculum, accreditation and
registration
standards. Public Health
Nutrition, 29(1), e27. DOI:
[10.1017/S1368980025101705](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980025101705)

Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Med-Tech &
Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG):

SDG 3: Good Health & Well-
Being

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Why it Matters

The findings from this research are relevant in the context of evolving healthcare priorities, where prevention and early intervention are increasingly emphasised. Supporting healthcare professionals to engage with nutrition in routine care may contribute to reducing modifiable risk factors and improving longer-term health outcomes. Primary care settings are particularly important in this regard, given their role as an accessible and trusted point of contact for the public. Opportunities exist to strengthen nutrition capacity through both undergraduate education and Continuing Professional Development (CPD) for those already in practice. However, any approach must be feasible within existing systems and mindful of workforce pressures. Further research is needed to identify approaches that are effective, practical and do not place additional burden on healthcare professionals.

What's Next?

Internationally, a substantial body of research has examined nutrition education in healthcare, with ongoing developments in contexts such as the UK demonstrating gradual progress in embedding nutrition within training and practice. At the same time, evidence suggests that nutrition remains inconsistently integrated across many professions. Building on this wider evidence base, there is a need for further research in the Irish context to understand how nutrition can be embedded effectively and consistently across education and practice settings. Future work could explore how nutrition education is delivered, how practitioners engage with it, and what models are sustainable across different disciplines. Ensuring that approaches remain practical for all stakeholders, including educators, healthcare professionals and patients, will be central to any meaningful progression.

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